

Pulsate

PHOTONICS²¹

PHOTONICS PUBLIC PRIVATE PARTNERSHIP

PULSATE PLAYBOOK for (E)DIHs

A toolkit created for European Digital Innovation Hubs and SMEs that are willing to implement Laser-Based Advanced & Additive Manufacturing technologies into their environment.

About PULSATE

PULSATE is a part of the Horizon2020 programme called I4MS funded by the European Commission with the goal to accelerate the design, development and uptake of advanced digital technologies by the European Manufacturing industry to empower personalised products and to facilitate cost-effective small-scale production. One of these digitalisation technologies that the PULSATE project is focused on is Laser Technology. To boost and support the uptake, PULSATE has supported end-users companies that are willing to implement Laser-Based Advanced & Additive Manufacturing technologies into their environment.

PULSATE project brings together a strong consortium comprising six competence centres (**AIMEN**, **FTMC**, **MTC**, **SINTEF**, **Fraunhofer** and **CEA**) with high-level expertise in Laser Technologies and digitisation, the European Photonics Industry Consortium (**EPIC**) to support the acceleration of EU innovative scale-up initiatives, and two highly innovative SMEs (**CLESGO** & **FundingBox**) to establish and support the Digital Agora platform, maintain a Marketplace of digital services and to manage the mechanisms of financial support to selected companies and the connection with (E)DIHs across all Europe.

www.pulsate.eu

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Objective & Value Proposition

OBJECTIVE OF THE PLAYBOOK

The objective of the toolkit is to assist European Digital Innovation Hubs ((E)DIHs) and SMEs in implementing Laser-Based Advanced & Additive Manufacturing technologies into their operations.

Information about Lasers and its advantages.

Assistance in overcoming challenges.

Access to the PULSATE network.

Training, technical webinars and events.

The Digital Agora to connect and collaborate.

What does PULSATE offer?

VALUE PROPOSITION FOR SMES:

- **Reduced barriers to Laser Technologies adoption:** PULSATE addresses the key challenges faced by SMEs in adopting Laser Technologies, including cost, complexity, skills, and awareness.
- **Increased competitiveness:** Laser Technologies can help SMEs create high-quality, innovative products, giving them a competitive edge.
- **Improved efficiency and agility:** Laser Technology can streamline production processes and make SMEs more responsive to market changes.
- **Access to a network of experts and resources:** PULSATE connects SMEs with a network of competence centres, (E)DIHs, and other industry players, providing access to a wealth of knowledge and support.
- **Long-term sustainability:** PULSATE's focus on long-term sustainability ensures that SMEs will have ongoing access to Laser Technologies resources and expertise beyond the project's lifetime.

VALUE PROPOSITION FOR (E)DIHS:

- **Enhanced support for SME members:** PULSATE equips (E)DIHs with the tools and resources to effectively guide their SME members on the Laser Technology adoption journey.
- **Increased innovation within the region:** By facilitating Laser Technologies adoption among SMEs, (E)DIHs can contribute to regional economic growth and innovation.
- **Stronger network and collaboration opportunities:** PULSATE fosters collaboration between (E)DIHs and other stakeholders within the Laser Technology ecosystem.

In essence, PULSATE offers a comprehensive support system for SMEs and (E)DIHs, enabling them to overcome the hurdles of Laser Technologies adoption and unlock the technology's full potential for increased competitiveness and innovation.

ABOUT LASER-BASED MANUFACTURING

Laser technology has become a transformative force across numerous industries. At its core, a laser generates a tight beam of light, allowing for incredibly precise manipulation of materials. This has led to the development of groundbreaking processes and products in manufacturing, healthcare, and communication.

In the manufacturing world, laser-based techniques have become essential for a variety of tasks. They offer unmatched precision for intricate designs and minimal material waste. Laser cutting, for instance, is widely used in everything from aerospace to medical devices. Laser welding creates exceptionally strong bonds with minimal heat, perfect for delicate components. Even drilling microscopic holes with high precision becomes possible with lasers, making them crucial for applications like microfluidics in medical devices.

The impact of laser technology reaches far beyond manufacturing. In healthcare, lasers play a vital role in various procedures, from surgery and diagnostics to therapeutic applications. The backbone of modern communication networks relies on lasers that transmit information through optical fibers. Even scientific research utilizes lasers as indispensable tools for groundbreaking experiments and discoveries.

By facilitating technology transfer, knowledge sharing, and financial support, PULSATE opens doors for innovative uses of lasers in sectors like:

- **Automotive:** Lasers can revolutionize prototyping, lightweight component creation, and even on-demand customization for vehicles.
- **Textile & Clothing:** Precise laser cutting and welding can enable intricate designs and personalized garment production.
- **Customized Electronics:** Laser technologies offers highly precise material manipulation for miniaturized and high-performance electronics.
- **Industrial Machinery:** Laser-based techniques can improve component precision, leading to more efficient and durable machinery.

PULSATE services

PULSATE sets-up and consolidates a robust and open PAN European Network, to promote and facilitate the adoption of Laser-Based Advanced Additive Manufacturing technologies. PULSATE serves as a Single-Entry Point to support SMEs and Mid caps by connecting European Digital Innovation Hubs, top class Competence Centres, Public Institutions, Standardization Organizations, Financing and Business Development entities. PULSATE will also offer training, technical webinars and brokerage and matchmaking events.

1. Unified Platform: Seamlessly connect with SMEs across Europe through our comprehensive service platform, focusing on sectors such as aerospace, automotive, medical devices, industrial machinery, customized electronics, and textiles. Grow your client base with direct access to a pool of SMEs in need of your (E)DIH expertise.

2. Knowledge Exchange: Be a leader in Laser Manufacturing and stay ahead the competitors. Benefit from practical insights and best practices through webinars and collaborative events, ensuring your (E)DIH is at the forefront of technological advancements.

3. Matchmaking Mechanism: Pulsate's targeted approach links SMEs seeking Laser Manufacturing services with (E)DIHs offering them. This strategic alignment ensures your (E)DIH's services directly meet the needs of SMEs, fostering effective collaboration and ensuring expectations alignment, on top of providing you with hot leads to grow your business.

4. Regional Expansion: Europe is truly borderless and so should be ambitions of SMEs to expand. Through our programmes we foster regional expansion and accessing expertise of a (E)DIH on the ground is a great way to pave the success for a foreign SME. Help yourself to get discovered by being a part of the easily searchable network.

5. Training Opportunities: Access specialized training modules covering essential aspects to enhance your (E)DIH's capabilities:

- Advanced Manufacturing (AM) standards
- Laser technology trends
- Design rules and best practices in Laser-Based Manufacturing
- Laser applications
- Laser equipment and safety
- Digitization and product lifecycle management

DIGITAL AGORA

The Digital Agora is a digital ecosystem, where manufacturers and ICT experts get together, discover one another, and build trustworthy business relationships. On the one hand, manufacturers can look for ICT-related know-how, interact with experts and other peers, and find experts with proven solutions for specific challenges. On the other hand, the ICT experts can respond to challenges posed by manufacturers, promote and showcase their solutions and infrastructures, and offer their experience and know-how.

PULSATE success stories

The PULSATE project has been a driving force in advancing Laser-Based Advanced & Additive Manufacturing technologies. This collection of success stories showcases how PULSATE has empowered companies to adopt and integrate Laser Technologies solutions, leading to significant improvements in productivity, efficiency, and product quality.

Explore these stories and discover how Laser Technology is revolutionising manufacturing.

BARRELCLAD: Automated Laser Cladding for High-Quality Twin Barrels

This project developed a cost-effective, automated system for applying wear-resistant coatings to the inside of large twin barrels using laser cladding. Previously, this process was slow, manual, and prone to defects. BARRELCLAD's innovations overcome these challenges by:

- Designing a special high-power cladding nozzle for efficient application
- Implementing real-time machine control for consistent quality
- Using advanced monitoring to ensure optimal process parameters

By automating and improving control, BARRELCLAD enables reliable, defect-free production of high-quality twin barrels.

LAMELLATED: 3D-Printing High-Performance Thermoelectric Devices

This project is developing a new 3D printing process (SLM) to create thermoelectric devices (TEGs) that are more efficient and cost-effective than current methods. Traditional TEG production wastes a lot of material and limits design options. LAMELLATED tackles this by:

- Using lasers to directly print TEGs in their final shape, eliminating material waste
- Enabling the use of new materials and designs for improved performance

This technology has the potential to revolutionise the TEG industry by creating high-performance devices at a lower cost

FLASP: Bringing Laser Peening to New Places

FLASP (Fibered Laser Shock Peening) is a revolutionary new method for strengthening metal components. Traditional laser peening is expensive, complex, and limited in reach. FLASP solves these problems by using a fibre optic cable to deliver the laser beam. This allows for:

- Treating complex shapes and hard-to-reach areas
- Robotic integration for automated processing
- Safer operation with no exposed lasers
- Reduced maintenance and consumable costs

FLASP offers significant advantages over conventional peening techniques, making it ideal for applications in aerospace, energy etc.

For more success stories please check the website [here](http://www.pulsate.eu).

FAQ

1. How can I help my SME members adopt Laser Technology?

You can help your SME members adopt Laser Technology by:

- Providing information and education: Offer workshops, seminars, and other educational resources.
- Connecting SMEs with Laser Technology experts: Put your SME members in touch with laser experts who can provide them with guidance and support.
- Helping SMEs find funding for Laser Technology projects: Assist SMEs in finding funding for laser projects, such as grants and funds.
- Creating a network of Laser Technology adopters: Facilitate a network of Laser Technology adopters where SMEs can share best practices and learn from each other.

2. Who is standing behind the PULSATE project?

PULSATE project is a powerhouse team. It includes six top-notch competence centers (AIMEN, FTMC, MTC, SINTEF, Fraunhofer, and CEA) with expertise in laser manufacturing and digitization. There is also the European Photonics Industry Consortium (EPIC) on board to help speed up innovative projects by European startups. To round out the team, there are two forward-thinking SMEs (CLESGO & FundingBox). These SMEs are responsible for setting up and running the Digital Agora platform, managing a marketplace filled with digital services, and providing financial support to chosen companies. They also connect these companies with European Digital Innovation Hubs across Europe.

3. How to sign up to the platform?

The first step in using the Digital Agora requires the login / sign up of users, in order to be allowed to access the available functionality for publishing and using Marketplace Services and Community Interactions.

On the top right corner of the home page under ACCOUNTS a link to “Log In” is available. If the user already has an account, the user can use the known credentials to log in into the Digital Agora. If the user has no account yet, the user can click on the link to sign up.

Please check the [website](#) to get the answers to all your questions.

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Take the Next Step with PULSATE!

Join **PULSATE Community** today and transform the future of manufacturing with Laser Technologies. As a European Digital Innovation Hub, you have the unique opportunity to connect with a vast network of experts, access cutting-edge resources, and provide unmatched support to your SME members.

Here's how you can get started:

- 1. Explore Opportunities:** Visit our [Digital Agora platform](#) to discover the latest technological advancements and collaboration opportunities.
- 2. Engage with Experts:** Connect with leading competence centers, industry consortia, and innovative SMEs to gain valuable insights and support.
- 3. Participate in Training:** Enhance your knowledge and skills through our specialized training modules, webinars, and events.
- 4. Leverage Financial Support:** Access funding mechanisms designed to help your SMEs adopt and implement Laser Technologies effectively.
- 5. Join the Conversation:** Be part of our community by following us on [Twitter](#), [LinkedIn](#), and [YouTube](#) for updates and success stories.

Make a Difference: Empower your region with innovative laser technologies and drive economic growth. The future of manufacturing starts with you. Visit [PULSATE](#) and sign up today to begin your journey.

For more information, contact us at hello@pulsate.eu.

Together, let's shape the future of manufacturing!